

AFRICAN INTITUTE OF ADVANCED LEARNING

IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SOMALIA

Compiled by; Rahma Mahmoud Mohamed

A research report presented to the Department of
English Language of African Institute of
Advanced Learning as a partial fulfilment
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Diploma in English Language

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Declaration

I, Mrs. Rahma Mahmoud Mohamed, hereby declare that the comprehensive exploration into the Impact of social media in Somalia, presented in this project report, has been diligently conducted by me from 7th Sep to 31st Dec 2023. I affirm that this report is exclusive and has not been submitted to any other institution for a diploma in English language

Signature,

Date,

Background

My name is Rahma Mahmoud Mohamed I was born in Mogadishu Somalia I live with my parents and my siblings and I am 22 years old at University.

I started my first education in 2006 when I was 04 years old learning holy Quran in Madarasatu Khalid Binu Waleed and I have finished the holy Quran when I was 11 years old.

in 2013 I joined Imam Shafici primary and Secondary school and I started from grade one there , when I finished grade one I transferred my school Halane primary and secondary school and I start grade two there and now I am .

I joined African institute of advanced learning to learn English language.

Supervisor's approval

This is to certify that the information provided in the aforementioned declaration is accurate and true to the best of our knowledge.

Name,

Sign,

Dedication

In profound acknowledgment of the intellectual odyssey undertaken, this English Language Diploma project on the Impact of social media in Somalia stands as a testament to unwavering dedication, persistent effort, and a resolute commitment to unraveling the intricate dynamics of the digital landscape shaping our nation's communication paradigm. This work is dedicated to my family, whose steadfast support and unwavering belief in my capabilities have served as the driving force behind my relentless pursuit. Their sacrifices and understanding have fueled the essence of this endeavor.

Furthermore, my deepest gratitude extends to mentors and educators for their illuminating guidance, shaping my intellectual growth and providing invaluable insights into the nuanced socio- technological dynamics at play. This project serves as a tribute to the resilient people of Somalia, whose experiences have not only inspired but have also been the cornerstone of this exploration. May this work catalyze positive change, foster meaningful dialogue, and ignite innovative solutions in the digital era.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my heartfelt appreciation to all those who played a vital role in the successful culmination of my English language diploma project focusing on the Impact of social media in Somalia. I extend special gratitude to my project supervisor for their steadfast guidance and invaluable support throughout the intricate research process.

Acknowledgment is also due to the participants who generously shared their time and insights during the data collection phase, ensuring the richness of this study. Moreover, I appreciate the understanding and encouragement extended by my family and friends during the course of this project.

Finally, I extend my deep gratitude to my esteemed instructor, Mr. Namadowa Hassan, whose profound expertise and insightful guidance have been instrumental in shaping and refining this work on the Impact of social media in Somalia.

Preface

In an age marked by swift technological progress, the sway of social media has quietly become an undeniable catalyst shaping societies globally. This English language diploma project gently navigates the intricate dance between the digital realm and the socio-cultural fabric of Somalia, a nation gracefully balancing tradition and modernity. The venture into "The Impact of Social Media in Somalia" is a delicate exploration, aiming to illuminate the nuanced outcomes of digital interconnectedness in this distinctive context.

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Chapter one: Introduction

1.1 Understanding Social Media:

Definition:

Social media refers to online platforms and tools that enable individuals and communities to create, share, and exchange information, ideas, and multimedia content in a virtual environment.

Or Social media is a phrase, to look at each word individually.

Social means a way of communicating with others by sharing information with them and obtaining information from them.

Media means communication device, such as the Internet (TV, radio, and newspaper media are examples of more traditional types).

Key Characteristics:

1. **Connectivity:** Facilitates global communication and networking, allowing users to connect with people across the world.
2. **Content Sharing:** Users can share diverse content such as text, images, videos, and links, fostering interactive and dynamic communication.
3. **Real-time Interaction:** Provides instant communication and feedback, fostering real-time conversations and engagement.
4. **User-Generated Content:** Emphasizes the role of users as content creators, encouraging a participatory and collaborative online culture.

Popular Platforms:

1. **Facebook:** A platform for connecting with friends and family, sharing updates, and joining communities.
2. **Instagram:** Focused on visual content, particularly photos and short videos, promoting creativity and visual storytelling.
3. **Twitter:** Known for microblogging, allowing users to share thoughts, news, and updates in 280-character tweets.

4. LinkedIn: Geared towards professional networking, connecting individuals in a business and career-oriented context.

Impact:

Communication: Revolutionizes the way people communicate, breaking down geographical barriers.

Information Dissemination: Serves as a rapid and widespread channel for the dissemination of news and information.

Influencer Culture: Gives rise to influencers who leverage their online presence to impact opinions and trends.

Community Building: Fosters the creation of online communities based on shared interests, hobbies, or affiliations.

Challenges:

Privacy Concerns: Raises questions about the protection of personal information and data security.

Misinformation: The rapid spread of unverified information poses challenges to the accuracy of content.

Online Harassment: Instances of cyberbullying and harassment may occur within the social media space.

In summary, social media has become an integral part of modern communication, connecting people globally while presenting both opportunities and challenges.

1.2 Media: Pros and Cons

Advantages:

1. **Global Connectivity:** Social media facilitates instant communication and connection with individuals worldwide, fostering a sense of global community.
2. **Information Access:** Users can stay updated on news, trends, and events in real-time, enhancing knowledge and awareness.
3. **Networking Opportunities:** Social platforms provide a powerful tool for professional networking, job opportunities, and collaboration.
4. **Amplified Expression:** Individuals can express their thoughts, creativity, and opinions, fostering diverse voices and perspectives.

Disadvantages:

1. **Privacy Concerns:** Users may sacrifice personal privacy, as social media platforms often collect and share user data for targeted advertising.
2. **Cyberbullying and Harassment:** The anonymity of online interactions can lead to cyberbullying, harassment, and the spread of misinformation.
3. **Time Consumption:** Excessive use of social media can contribute to procrastination, reduced productivity, and negative impacts on mental health.
4. **Filter Bubbles:** Algorithms may create echo chambers, limiting exposure to diverse viewpoints and reinforcing pre-existing beliefs.

It is essential to navigate social media mindfully, balancing its benefits with the potential drawbacks for a positive online experience.

CHAPTER TWO: ISLAMIC PERSPECTIVE

2.1. Introduction:

In recent years, interactions between humans have completely changed with the appearance and development of computers and networks. Social relationships are going to start at the beginning of the web. People communicate, build relationships using social networks (Bandura, 1986). Today, social media adoption and use of a wide range of human life in every section. Muslims are not different from other societies, in the last few years, which has increased the use of social media trends. It has brought changes that can have a significant impact on the individual and group level of Muslim society. Social media is easy to use, easy to learn, and the ability to communicate public universality of speed (Davis, 1989).

Muslim Society Definition: A society in which Islamic culture is dominant. It's called also Islamic society. IJSHS, 2019; 3 (3): 95-114 99 • simply, defined as society "people in a defined area are a group of interactions and shared culture" (Renzetti & Curran, 2000). • Islamic society "for a logical and peaceful coexistence, an organization formed in accordance with the Divine Law" (Muslehuddin, 1977). Other scholars used the word Ummah instead of the word of Islamic society. They have quoted these words from the Holy Quran. In this context, the words Ummah and the village (Kuraiya) have been used for the society (Abdul Jabr Mohammad 1987).

Allah (SWT) said: "That is a nation which has passed on. It will have [the consequence of] what it earned and you will have what you have earned. And you will not be asked about what they used to do" (2:141). "That is because your Lord would not destroy the cities for wrongdoing while their people were unaware" (6:131).

Social media has become an integral part of contemporary society, influencing communication, information dissemination, and social interactions.

2.2. Islamic Values and Ethics:

Islam emphasizes values such as honesty, integrity, and respect for others. These principles should guide Muslims in their online presence.

2.3. Positive Engagement:

Encourage positive interactions on social media platforms.

Share knowledge, engage in meaningful discussions, and foster a sense of community.

2.4. Guarding Speech (Tongue):

The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) emphasized the importance of guarding one's speech.

Social media users should avoid spreading false information, gossip, and engaging in harmful discussions.

2.5. Privacy and Modesty:

Islam places a high value on privacy and modesty.

Muslims should be cautious about sharing personal information and adhere to Islamic principles of modesty in online behavior.

2.6. Promoting Virtue and Discouraging Vice:

Social media can be a platform to promote good and discourage evil.

Muslims should strive to share content that aligns with Islamic values and contribute positively to the online environment.

2.6. Digital Etiquette (Adab):

Adhering to the principles of digital etiquette is crucial.

Responding with kindness, avoiding offensive language, and respecting diverse opinions contribute to a healthy online community.

2.7. Avoiding Excessive Time Consumption:

Islam encourages moderation in all aspects of life, including the use of social media.

Muslims should be mindful of not letting excessive time on social media interfere with their daily responsibilities and religious obligations.

2.8. Seeking Knowledge and Guidance:

Use social media platforms to seek beneficial knowledge and guidance from reputable sources.

Platforms can be a tool for learning more about Islam, connecting with scholars, and fostering a deeper understanding of one's faith.

Conclusion:

While embracing the benefits of social media, Muslims should align their online presence with Islamic values, ensuring that their interactions contribute positively to society and adhere to the teachings of Islam.

CHAPTER THREE: GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

3.1: Overview of Global Perspective on Social Media

Introduction:

Social media has become an integral part of modern communication, connecting people across the globe.

The global perspective on social media highlights its impact on societies, cultures, and economies worldwide.

Key Points:

1. Cultural Exchange:

Social media platforms facilitate the exchange of cultural ideas, traditions, and experiences.

Users can engage with diverse content, gaining insights into different lifestyles, customs, and perspectives.

2. Global Activism:

Social media empowers individuals and communities to raise awareness about social issues on a global scale.

Movements such as #BlackLivesMatter and #MeToo have gained momentum globally, transcending geographical boundaries.

3. Business and Economy:

Social media has transformed global business dynamics by providing a platform for marketing and networking.

Companies can reach a global audience, and entrepreneurs can connect with collaborators and investors worldwide.

4. Language and Communication:

Language barriers are overcome through features like translation tools and emoji usage.

Social media fosters a diverse linguistic landscape, enabling communication beyond traditional linguistic boundaries.

3.2: Challenges and Future Trends

Challenges:

1. Misinformation and Fake News:

The rapid spread of misinformation poses challenges to global societies.

Fake news can fuel panic, affect public opinion, and even have political ramifications.

2. Privacy Concerns:

Global discussions on data privacy and surveillance have intensified.

Balancing the benefits of social media with the protection of user privacy remains a critical challenge.

Future Trends:

3. Virtual Reality (VR) Integration:

The future of social media may see increased integration with virtual reality.

VR platforms could provide more immersive and lifelike social interactions.

4. Augmented Reality (AR) Experiences:

AR features will likely enhance user experiences, offering new ways to interact with content.

This could impact industries such as gaming, education, and shopping.

5. Ethical AI and Content Moderation:

Stricter ethical guidelines and improved AI algorithms will be crucial for content moderation.

Balancing free expression with preventing harm and misinformation will be a key focus.

Conclusion:

Social media's global impact is multifaceted, influencing culture, activism, business, and communication. As the landscape evolves, addressing challenges and embracing future trends will be essential for creating a positive and inclusive global social media environment.

CHAPTER FOUR: AFRICA PERSPECTIVE

4.1: Introduction to Africa's Social Media Landscape Africa's Evolving Social Media Landscape

1. Overview of Social Media Usage:

Africa has witnessed a significant surge in social media usage over the past decade.

With a diverse population and rapidly expanding connectivity, social media plays a pivotal role in shaping communication and information dissemination.

2. Diverse Platforms and Preferences:

Africans engage with various social media platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, and local platforms like Mix and Naira land.

Preferences vary across regions and demographics, reflecting the continent's rich cultural tapestry.

3. Social Impact:

Social media serves as a catalyst for social and political movements, enabling citizens to voice concerns, organize protests, and foster community engagement.

It has also become a platform for showcasing African talent, culture, and entrepreneurship globally.

4. Challenges:

Despite the positive impact, challenges such as digital literacy, access, and concerns about misinformation persist.

Efforts are being made to bridge the digital divide and promote responsible online behavior.

4.2: Opportunities and Future Trends Unlocking Opportunities: Africa's Social Media Future

1. Economic Opportunities:

Social media platforms have become powerful tools for small businesses and entrepreneurs, facilitating e-commerce, marketing, and brand building.

Platforms like Jumia and Conga exemplify the potential for online commerce in Africa.

2. Youth Engagement:

Africa has a youthful population, and social media serves as a key platform for youth engagement, activism, and networking.

It provides a space for expressing creativity, fostering innovation, and connecting with global youth movements.

3. Tech Innovation and Local Platforms:

There is a growing trend of homegrown social media platforms catering to African audiences.

Examples include KudaBank, a Nigerian online bank, and lesson, an educational platform, showcasing Africa's potential for tech innovation.

4. Cultural Exchange:

Social media fosters cultural exchange within Africa and with the global community.

It allows Africans to share their rich traditions, art, and stories while also embracing and learning from diverse global cultures.

5. Looking Ahead:

The future holds immense potential for Africa's social media landscape, with ongoing efforts to address challenges and leverage opportunities for economic growth, social development, and cultural exchange.

Collaborations between governments, private sectors, and tech innovators are key to unlocking the full potential of social media in Africa.

CHAPTER FIVE: SOMALIA PERSPECTIVE

5.1: Overview of Somalia's Perspective on Social Media

Introduction:

Somalia, a country located in the Horn of Africa, has a unique perspective on social media influenced by its historical context and current socio-political landscape.

Historical Context:

Somalia has a complex history marked by civil wars, political instability, and economic challenges.

Traditional media outlets faced restrictions, leading to a reliance on alternative means of communication, including social media.

Social Media as a Tool for Connectivity:

Despite challenges, social media serves as a vital tool for connectivity in Somalia.

Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram facilitate communication among the Somali diaspora and provide a space for global connections.

Youth Empowerment and Expression:

The youth in Somalia actively engage in social media to express their views, share stories, and connect with a global audience.

Social media empowers the youth to voice their opinions, fostering a sense of participation in shaping the narrative of their country.

Challenges and Opportunities in Somalia's Social Media Landscape

Challenges:

Access and Infrastructure: Limited internet access and infrastructure challenges hinder widespread social media use.

Spread of Misinformation: Like many other nations, Somalia grapples with the spread of misinformation on social media, impacting public perception.

Opportunities:

Awareness and Advocacy: Social media platforms are utilized for raising awareness about social issues and advocating for change.

Economic Potential: Entrepreneurs and businesses explore social media as a means to market products and services, contributing to economic growth.

Government Regulation and Freedom of Expression:

Balancing government regulation with the need for freedom of expression remains a critical challenge.

Striking a balance that fosters a healthy information environment while respecting individual rights is essential.

Conclusion:

Somalia's perspective on social media is shaped by its historical context, providing both challenges and opportunities.

As the country continues to navigate these dynamics, social media remains a powerful tool for communication, expression, and connectivity in the Somali context.

5.2: Overview of Somalia's Social Media Landscape

Introduction:

Somalia, located in the Horn of Africa, has witnessed a significant transformation in its social media landscape in recent years.

Social Media Penetration:

Despite challenges such as limited internet infrastructure and access, social media usage is on the rise.

Mobile phones play a crucial role in accessing platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram.

Youth Engagement:

The majority of Somalia's population is under 30, contributing to a vibrant and dynamic online community.

Social media serves as a platform for youth to express opinions, share ideas, and engage in discussions on various topics.

Challenges:

Connectivity issues and limited access in rural areas pose challenges to widespread social media adoption.

Concerns about misinformation and the spread of fake news are prevalent, demanding increased digital literacy efforts.

5.3: Impact of Social Media on Somali Society

Information Sharing:

Social media platforms serve as vital sources for news and information dissemination in a country with a dynamic media landscape.

Instant updates on current events, humanitarian issues, and political developments are shared widely.

Community Building:

Social media fosters virtual communities that transcend geographical boundaries, allowing Somalis worldwide to connect, share experiences, and maintain cultural ties.

Platforms like WhatsApp play a crucial role in family communication and support networks.

Political Influence:

Social media has become a powerful tool for political activism, enabling citizens to voice concerns, organize movements, and engage with political leaders.

It has played a role in shaping public opinion and mobilizing support for various causes.

Conclusion:

Somalia's social media landscape reflects a dynamic blend of challenges and opportunities, with the youth playing a pivotal role in shaping the online narrative.

Efforts to address connectivity issues and enhance digital literacy will contribute to a more inclusive and informed social media environment in the country.

5.4 Overview of Somalia's Social Media Landscape "Navigating Somalia's Digital Landscape"

Introduction:

Somalia's social media scene has witnessed significant growth in recent years, reflecting the nation's increasing connectivity and engagement with the digital world.

Social media platforms play a pivotal role in shaping public discourse, connecting communities, and serving as a platform for expression in Somalia.

Platform Diversity:

Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram are among the most popular social media platforms, providing Somalis with spaces to share news, personal stories, and cultural expressions.

The widespread use of mobile phones has fueled the rapid adoption of social media, making it a powerful tool for communication and information dissemination.

Challenges:

Despite the positive aspects, challenges such as misinformation, fake news, and online hate speech are prevalent. The digital divide and limited access to reliable information contribute to these issues.

Efforts are underway to address these challenges through digital literacy initiatives and collaborations between the government and tech companies.

Slide 2: Social Media's Impact on Somali Society

5.5: "Influence and Impact: Social Media in Somalia"

Role in Civic Engagement:

Social media platforms serve as a space for civic engagement, enabling citizens to voice opinions, discuss political issues, and participate in activism.

The #Somalia Rising movement on Twitter, for example, exemplifies the power of social media in mobilizing people for social and political change.

Economic Opportunities:

Social media has become a marketplace for entrepreneurs, allowing them to showcase products and services, reaching a broader audience both domestically and internationally.

Platforms like Instagram have provided a platform for Somali businesses to thrive, fostering economic growth and innovation.

Cultural Expression:

Social media enables the global Somali diaspora to connect with their roots, share cultural content, and stay informed about events in Somalia.

Through platforms like YouTube and Instagram, Somali artists, poets, and content creators showcase their work, contributing to the preservation and promotion of Somali culture.

Conclusion:

Somalia's perspective on social media reflects a dynamic interplay between opportunities and challenges.

As the digital landscape continues to evolve, there is a need for concerted efforts to harness the positive aspects of social media while addressing its drawbacks for the benefit of Somali society.

5.6: Reflections on the Journey:

As we conclude this exploration into the impact of social media on Somali society, it is essential to reflect on the key findings and insights garnered throughout our journey. From the transformation of traditional communication to the fostering of cultural identity online, social media has emerged as a powerful catalyst for change in Somalia. The narratives shared, the challenges unveiled, and the triumphs celebrated all contribute to a nuanced understanding of the intricate relationship between technology and society.

Through our exploration, we have witnessed social media's role in connecting the Somali diaspora, amplifying grassroots movements, empowering businesses, and democratizing access to information. It has not only served as a tool for communication but also as a dynamic force shaping cultural expression, economic landscapes, and activism within the nation.

5.7: The Continued Evolution of social media in Somalia:

As we look forward, it becomes evident that the journey of social media's evolution in Somalia is far from reaching its destination. The landscape is marked by constant change, propelled by technological advancements, cultural shifts, and societal dynamics. New possibilities are on the horizon, promising further integration of social media into various facets of Somali life.

The challenges ahead, including digital divides, misinformation, and the delicate balance between regulation and freedom, will require continued attention and collaborative efforts. The dynamic nature of social media demands adaptive strategies, both from individuals and institutions, to harness its potential for positive societal impact.

The forward-looking perspective emphasizes the need for vigilance, responsibility, and innovation. Technological advancements will unfold, influencing how social media shapes the

Future of Somalia. It is a journey that calls for the active participation of government, influencers, businesses, and the wider community to ensure that the benefits of social media continue to outweigh its challenges.

In conclusion, our exploration into the impact of social media on Somalia reveals a complex and multifaceted relationship. As we bid farewell to this chapter of our study, we acknowledge that

the story of social media in Somalia is ongoing, with each post, share, and interaction contributing to the narrative of a nation navigating the digital age.

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African Institute of advanced learning

All this research I got from a lot of places whether it becomes in Internet or schools.

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